

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DIGITAL UPGRADE IN CLASSICAL LEAN PRODUCTION SYSTEM IN MANUFACTURING ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

A continuous focus on improvement helps to improve the effectiveness of processes, organizational capabilities and customer satisfaction, identify and investigate the root causes of nonconformities with subsequent preventive and corrective actions, anticipate and respond to internal and external risks and opportunities in a timely manner, achieve breakthrough improvements, apply knowledge more effectively, use innovation. The system of lean production in Kazakhstan is still young concept that is not used by each manufacturing company in our country. However, international experience shows that implementation of lean production in manufacturing can bring higher productivity with same or lower costs. Classical systems also can be improved in the case of new technological developments and directly introduced in manufacturing companies. In this article we observe the classical lean production system with upgrade using new digitalization tools.

Keywords: lean production, production process, manufacturing, operation management, 5S.

The effective construction of production processes and the organization of labor at the enterprise significantly affect not only the speed of the enterprise, but also the amount of material and intangible resources expended. These indicators are especially relevant in the current crisis conditions. After all, many Kazakhstani enterprises are faced with the problems of unprofitable manufacturing of products, reorganization of the management hierarchy of enterprise management, reduction of production staff, irrational use of equipment. These are the consequences of the imperfection of the construction of the production process. Ensuring the use of all elements of production is possible with the use of progressive forms of labor organization and production processes. However, in practice, many production units are not organized in the best way.

The methodology of the organization of the production process is a set of combinations of basic elements, methods and techniques of organizing the production process in space and time. It should be noted that the methodology and project management tools are widely used in all areas of purposeful and project-oriented activities of manufacturing enterprises. Thus, it should be noted that the rational construction of the production process is a prerequisite for allowing the enterprise to function effectively in the current conditions of a market economy.

Regardless of the area of use, the lean manufacturing system helps to significantly increase the efficiency of work activities and significantly reduce waste [1]. The classical model of the 5S system is shown in fig. 1.

Figure 1. 5S model in production process

Foreign studies have shown that the classical model has a number of characteristic drawbacks: losses related to the first and second kind, low efficiency of flow processes within the enterprise, low degree of continuity of the production process, "human factor", unnecessary movements. It is necessary to adequately combine the principles of traditional management with the achievements of modern information technologies. In addition, enterprises usually use manual collection of a large amount of primary data, which significantly increases the likelihood of errors and inaccuracies in the implementation of communications. Incorrect data taken into account when making a decision can adversely affect the subsequent work of the company [2]. The volume of primary data also largely affects the completeness and correctness of the subsequent management strategy.

In the classical model, communication processes, as a rule, are organized according to the "ring" scheme. Therefore, a significant drawback of the 5S scheme is the weak consistency of communication relations in terms of the type of sources and receivers of information, the nature and content of the information transmitted during cross communications.

The lean model achieves its goal of minimizing costs, but becomes very inertial and inflexible when changes are introduced. The classic model works well in mass and sustainable production [3]. The current socio-economic situation is characterized by a rapidly changing environment and a smaller scale of production. The traditional logistics management model of lean production in such conditions becomes inflexible, slowly responds to the challenges of the external environment and, therefore, it needs to be improved.

In production, it is necessary to independently control the equipment used and its effectiveness. The implementation of this function is a very laborious and long-term task. In this case, the simplest and most acceptable way out of the situation would be to switch to a "wheel" communication scheme with a central communication module acting as an interface between the links of the 5S system [4]. To do this, it is proposed to improve the 5S model by adding a digital communication module D (from Digital) to it. This improved model will be called "5S + D"

This improvement does not destroy the existing lean management system, but complements it, giving the necessary flexibility and dynamics to the decision-making process in case of any rapid changes. Module D (Digital) is responsible for the communication of all five components of the system and is a tool for managing all binders. This will lead to a clear vision of all problem areas and shortages on the production line, as well as a quick response to eliminate all shortcomings. Which will further eliminate excess inventory, waste, production downtime and improve efficiency. This communicator will be a universal module or a group of modules that act as a user and software interface, which will be designed to automatically collect and process data from various devices, sensors, instruments through the introduction of a unified information presentation system and their transformation on a single digital platform [5].

Communication module D (Digital) is a lean logistics management module that acts as a user, graphical and software interface between the elements of the 5S system. The principle of operation of the communication module is based on the coordination and analysis of information from various sensors and sources such as CNC machines, robotic welding complexes, IC, as well as system users and the issuance of analog and digital signals. The module provides measurement, conversion, archiving of communicative information, display of results using a graphical interface on the monitor and transmission of measured and received data on the amount of residue in the warehouse, on the analysis of finished parts for a particular product, etc.

The software of the communicators operates on the basis of a real-time operating system with information stored in a database. On the digital platform, statistics are issued that provide management decision-making. The digitalization program will be formed as a tool for improving technological and operational processes, achieving a new level of service. Its implementation will ensure an increase in the reliability of investment efficiency, labor productivity, indicators of observability of the main and auxiliary equipment.

The introduction of digitalization into lean manufacturing will solve the problems associated with process management, information collection and real-time problem identification. Digital twins and virtual reality enable fast and cheap experiments in a simulated environment. Additive manufacturing challenges conventional manufacturing processes. The use of mobile devices increases the speed and accuracy of inspections in hard-to-reach production areas.

To implement the process of digital transformation of production, it is necessary to form a new link in the organizational structure, which will further form and ensure the functioning of the "digital communicator D (Digital)". This link will be responsible for the management and control of technological lines for the production of a particular product. Competent decision-making based on the analysis of big data obtained using the module from various sources and transformed into a digital platform is used to improve the efficiency of industrial production and logistics, monitor the state of fixed assets and their predictive maintenance [4].

Implementation of the 5S+D "Lean Production" system will ensure the coordinated work of all workshops and eliminate unforeseen equipment shutdowns due to clear knowledge and resource management using the D communicator. With the help of a clear idea of the quantity of finished and purchased products stored in the warehouse, the consumer value of the product increases. The use of the 5S + D "Lean Manufacturing" system will help change production processes, achieve high coordination between the work of departments, and reduce the amount of inventory.

The communicative component of the 5s + D system will eliminate excess production through a clear vision of all stages of production and knowledge of a particular quantity of the product we need for further assembly, welding, machining. All hidden problems that hinder the optimization of production will be visible.

Implementation of lean production system in Kazakhstan is still raw concept that many companies still educate in order to implement in their manufacturing systems. However, many Kazakhstani companies already successfully implemented lean manufacturing and get competitive advantage from that. In addition, Kazakhstan extremely fast develop in the sector of digitalization and many intelligent systems already introduced in manufacturing companies. Nowadays we still can implement classical lean production systems with support of innovation technologies even in companies that have never used lean production systems before.

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